

WOMEN'S ROLE IN NATION BUILDING

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For many centuries, a woman was the keeper of the hearth, while everything that had to do with the outside world was taken over by a man. This, of course, gave him the right to consider a woman much lower in status than himself. But in our time of technological progress, scientific discoveries and feminism, the situation has changed dramatically. A woman in modern society has a completely different status and vocation, she has other values and needs that make us reconsider our views on the female role in today's world.

The role of a woman in modern society is no longer limited to household duties, caring for children, raising them and serving their legal spouse. Now this position is considered obsolete, and women who still choose it are perceived as supporters of conservative beliefs, who almost voluntarily give themselves into slavery to a man. In fact, this approach is erroneous in specific situations, when the representative of the weaker sex sees her vocation in preserving family values and does not seek to separate her own achievements from the success of her husband. After all, the embodiment of personal ambitions, career growth and the status of independence, at least financially, do not attract everyone to this day. Many women do not single out these criteria as an end in themselves, preferring to fully serve the family. But here comes the other extreme, since the position of a woman in modern society today is considered not only as a housewife, faithful wife and good mother. It often turns out that relatives and friends of girls, and first of all their parents, from adolescence inspire them that the main thing in life is not a strong family, but a stable social status. Therefore, before you commit yourself to marriage, you need to be firmly on your feet and be financially independent. The arguments in this matter are warnings that if suddenly the spouse leaves the family, if the children are left without a father, if something else terrible happens, the woman should be ready for this. In fact, the position of a woman in modern society suggests such fears, because today divorce is not considered something reprehensible or catastrophic. So the probability of the destruction of marriage bonds is growing every year: people become more categorical and often do not want to endure even the slightest inconvenience in a marriage union.

It turns out that the task of a woman in the modern world is, first of all, to achieve success in work, career growth, material independence, and only then

the status of a wife and mother. Thus, there is a so-called reassessment of values, which in turn leads to a rethinking of the meaning of the family and marital relations in the life of the weaker sex.

Due to the fact that the social role of women in modern society has undergone radical changes over the past decades, naturally, the status of the representatives of the weaker sex is also changing. So, contemporary psychologists tend to consider the following main categories of women: leaders, careerists, housewives, owners of free professions. Women leaders in terms of character traits in many ways resemble men: they are purposeful, confident in their own abilities and achieve everything on their own, without relying on anyone's help. Self-realization is the main goal of careerists who always put work and success in their careers in the first place. Only after such results can they afford to think about creating a family and planning children. The status of a woman in modern society who has chosen the role of a housewife, as a rule, is not viewed from the best side today.

The study of the role of women in nation building is necessary for future specialists who are called upon to actively deal with the resolution of a wide range of social problems, both in general and at the individual, private level. The acquired knowledge will contribute to the formation of not only professional, but also moral qualities of students.

Many researchers note that a man becomes masculine, and a woman becomes feminine in the process of assimilation by them of the corresponding roles accepted in this society. However, it would be absurd to believe that the role is an exclusively social norm, embedded in the consciousness of the individual.

The position of women in nation building has constantly attracted the attention of scientific thought. In modern society, which is constantly undergoing changes in the sphere of society and culture, the "women's issue" has become extremely relevant: the position of a woman is increasingly dependent on the situation in society, on how quickly and successfully social and cultural reform and the reform of the legal aspects of life, the development of secular started inside the institution of the family.

The status of women is a kind of barometer that is sensitive to the demographic, economic, environmental and political changes taking place in society. A modern woman is independent in all spheres of life: she independently plans her own life, receives a higher education and the right to work, she decides whether to marry or live in a civil marriage, she chooses a man for herself, has the right to sexual freedom and birth control.

Modern girls have lost the feeling of motherhood, something that was laid in them from the very beginning. They put a career in the foreground, and the family has lost its meaning for them. This is dangerous because the childbearing age will pass - a time that can no longer be returned, and the woman will lose the chance to become a mother.

The conducted research determines that it is important for a modern girl to be clearly aware of her role in society and follow it. Accordingly, it is necessary to create conditions for this at the university that will help female students to harmoniously combine and successfully implement those social roles that are important and interesting to them.

It should also be noted that, taking into account the key role of women in raising a healthy generation, a number of programs have been adopted in Uzbekistan to provide them with social support. In addition, employment contracts include benefits such as financial assistance to women during pregnancy and childbirth, maternity leave until the children are 2 or 3 years old, and a reduction in working hours by one hour if they have children under three years of age.

The formation of Uzbekistan as a legal democratic state with a strong civil society is the most important factor in the growth of social and political activity of women. It is obvious that over the years of independence, Uzbekistan has already managed to achieve a lot on this path. It is also undoubted that the favorable conditions for life, work and upbringing of the younger generation created and being created for women will continue to serve as a major support for them and Uzbekistan as a whole to achieve even greater achievements and success

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